

A simple route to fabricate strong boride hierarchical composites for use at ultra-high temperature

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Graphical abstract

Abstract

A simple method to obtain a highly refractory HfB₂-based ceramic nano-composite is presented. The boride was hot pressed with additions of SiC and WC particles and subsequently annealed at 2100°C for 2 hours. The annealing procedure was beneficial for high temperature strength, which increased by about 300 MPa in the 1500°C to 1800°C temperature range compared to the as-sintered material. Peak strengths of 850 MPa at 1500°C and 650 MPa at 1800°C were achieved due to two main microstructural changes. First, rounded SiC particles that were surrounded by a silica-based glass in the as-sintered ceramics evolved into platelets with mostly clean grain boundaries after heat treatment. In addition, the (Hf,W)B₂ solid solution that formed as shells around HfB₂ grain cores during densification reached an equilibrium state after annealing that revealed nano-texturing of the shell, which constituted a nano-composite with metallic W nano-particles embedded within HfB₂ grains. These two features combined to contribute to refractoriness and increased strength at elevated temperature. The unique findings reported in this study launch significant opportunities for ceramic development, manufacturing, and applications.

Keywords: hierarchical material; self-assembly; nano-structured composite; high temperature strength.

1. Introduction

Ceramic nano-composites have attracted enormous interest due to exceptional properties that they display as compared to their corresponding micro-composites.[1] The term “nano-composite” refers to multiphase materials, where at least one constituent phase has dimensions below 100 nm.[2] The interest in this type of materials is due to the simultaneous increase of hardness, strength, and local fracture toughness provided by the nano-sized inclusions. The inclusions trigger pinning mechanisms and, thus, limit matrix grain growth, and/or activate crack bridging and deflection mechanisms.[3,4] One necessary condition to exploit the full structural properties potential of the nano-composite concept is to achieve a homogeneous distribution of second nano-sized phase. This is a challenging issue, particularly when high volume fractions of inclusions are desired. In fact, due to their extremely high specific surface area, nanoparticles have an intrinsically high tendency to agglomerate.[3-5] Production routes range from traditional mixing and milling of single-phase ceramic powders to more complex methods including, but not limited to, polymer precursors, vapor phase reaction, sol-gel, and co-precipitation synthesis.[3,4] Whilst conventional powder processing routes are simple, they do not guarantee homogeneous particle packing, which affects the densification behavior and may result in large flaws after sintering. On the other side, more advanced synthesis methods comprise delicate or complex procedures. Hence, their use is mostly limited to the lab-scale.

Here, we present a simple method to obtain a micro/nano composite, with rounded nano-particles occupying intra-granular positions inside a boride matrix with micron-sized grains, that displays outstanding strength up to 1800°C. The choice of the boride matrix is based on its combination of physical, chemical, and engineering properties of this class of materials, which are known as ultra-high temperature ceramics (UHTCs) and are candidates use in extreme environments such as those involved in hypersonic aerospace and propulsion applications.[6-8]

Despite intense research on materials for extreme environments over the last 20 years, mechanical behavior of such ceramics above 1600°C remains poorly investigated. Thus, it is still necessary to validate these materials at temperatures where they are foreseen to operate. Recently, thanks to the development of ultra-high temperature mechanical testing capabilities, it has been possible to perform studies at temperatures of 2000°C or above, which has revealed microstructure-property relationships of borides at elevated temperatures.[9-12] Previous studies of diborides have also outlined some guidelines for the design of highly refractory ceramics with improved strength at elevated temperature.[11,13-18] Starting from the macro scale, the ceramic should be fully dense, without microcracks or other flaws, have an average grain size between 1 and 2 μm , have grain boundaries free of low-melting temperature phases, and, possibly, contain homogeneously dispersed refractory second phases. Furthermore, another factor which seems to positively affect the elevated temperature strength is the presence of concentrated dislocation networks within the grains of the matrix phase. The importance of the dislocation substructure

is related to the ability to store energy within grains before fracture. In this respect, solid solution additions (X) that have weak X-B bonds reduce the barrier for dislocation nucleation and, hence, contribute to strength retention at elevated temperatures.[19]

A fascinating microstructural feature that results in dislocation accumulation is the core-shell sub-structure, which spontaneously forms when borides are sintered at specific temperatures in the presence of transition metal compounds.[20,21] In these materials, the core is a nominally pure diboride grain seed, while the shell is a solid solution that contains variable amounts of a second transition metal cation. The particular shell structure and composition that develop depend on the transition metal added and the sintering parameters. The shells are substitutional solid solutions whereby the original transition metal species is replaced by another. Further, the substitution might have a larger atomic radius and result in expansion of the unit cell volume, or a smaller radius and result in a decrease in the unit cell volume. Larger cations produce a compressive state in the shell, whilst smaller will generate tensile strains. The measured lattice constants of the solid solution shell typically result in linear variations with composition.[22] The distorted lattice makes diffusion more difficult and results in stronger materials. Borides displaying extremely high bending strength and compression resistance at elevated temperature, and even enhanced oxidation behavior have all been shown to feature core-shell grains.[13,23]

Complete solid solution is thought to be desirable for enhanced thermo-mechanical performance; however, mutual solubility between refractory borides is defined by size factor considerations, i.e. solid solution in diborides obeys Hume-Rothery's rules.[22] Slight variations in solubility might also be influenced by processing conditions, such as temperature and application of external pressure.[20,24] Kinetic factors such as the length of heat treatments may also lead to variations in shell chemistry and spatial extent.

Since our previous report of enhanced elevated temperature strength for ZrB₂-SiC-WC ceramics,[25] we have studied the influence of SiC and WC additions also on the strength behavior of HfB₂. The choice of these secondary phases is jointly motivated by both improved oxidation behavior and also enhanced densification based on the ability of these additives to remove native oxides from diboride particle surfaces. In addition, W-compounds, such as WC, and in particular W, have extremely high melting points, above 2800°C, suitable for the applications envisaged for UHTCs.

In an attempt to further improve the elevated temperature strength HfB₂-SiC-WC ceramics, annealing was performed to investigate its effect on the evolution of the core-shell structure, the in-situ development of a nano-composite, and the concomitant effect on the strength. Heat treatment at elevated temperatures may induce redistribution of chemical species or the elimination of grain-boundary phases due to reaction or migration of liquid to the specimen surface where it could evaporate. In particular, fracture toughness has been shown to benefit from heat treatments that promote recrystallization of grain boundary phases, resulting in new phases that are more refractory.[26] Positive consequences have also been demonstrated on the elevated temperature mechanical properties of both SiC and Si₃N₄ structural

ceramics[27,28] and, more recently, on UHTCs.[29–31] Analysis by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) on ZrB₂ ceramics fractured at elevated temperatures suggested that additional phases may form and/or dislocation or stacking fault density may change during heating.[25,31]

The purpose of the present manuscript is to study the effect of heat treatments on the microstructure, phase assemblage, and elevated temperature mechanical behavior of HfB₂-SiC-WC ceramics.

2. Experimental procedure

Commercial powders were used to prepare the ceramics. The major phase was HfB₂ (Cerac Inc. USA, 99.5% pure, -325 mesh, d₅₀: 1.64 μm, Zr: 0.2 wt%, Fe: 0.02 wt%) with additions of 5 vol% WC (Treibacher Industries AG, Germany, grade 05, d₅₀: 0.5 μm, purity: 99.5%) and 5 vol% β-SiC (Starck, Germany, BF12, d₅₀: 0.6 μm, purity > 99%, O: 0.9 wt%) as secondary phases.

The powders were batched into a polyethylene bottle and ball-milled for 24 hours in absolute ethanol using SiC milling media. Subsequently, the slurry was dried using a rotary evaporator and then sieved through a 150 μm metallic screen. A 30 mm diameter pellet was cold compacted using a uniaxial press with 20 MPa applied pressure. The green pellet was placed into a graphite die located inside the vacuum chamber of the hot-press furnace (Ing. Allaria, Turin, Italy). The inner walls of the graphite die were protected by a graphitized foil that was 0.5 mm thick and protected by a BN spray coating. The pellet was then hot-pressed under vacuum in the range of 0.1-1 mbar using an induction-heated graphite die with a constant uniaxial pressure of 30 MPa applied during ramping at 20°C/min up to 1930°C. This temperature, set on the basis of the shrinkage curve, was maintained for 40 minutes until no further hot press ram movement was recorded. The temperature was monitored by means of an optical pyrometer focused into a blind hole drilled into the external surface of the graphite die. At the end of the final dwell, the furnace power was switched off and the furnace was allowed to cool at its natural rate. To obtain a nano-composite, post-densification annealing was performed in a resistance-heated graphite furnace under a flowing argon atmosphere (~1 atm) at 2100°C for 120 min.

The bulk density was measured by Archimedes' method using distilled water at 25°C, while the theoretical density was computed according to the rule of mixtures assuming the nominal batched composition. Crystalline phases of the sintered ceramic were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD, mod. D8 Advance - Bruker, Germany) analysis that used Si powder as an internal standard to quantify peak shift. The microstructure of the as-sintered and annealed ceramic was analyzed on fractured and polished surfaces by field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM, mod. ΣIGMA, ZEISS NTS GmbH, Germany) coupled to energy dispersive X-ray micro-analysis (EDS, mod. INCA Energy 300, Oxford instruments, UK). Key microstructural features like residual porosity, mean grain size and volumetric content of the secondary phases, were evaluated using computerized image analysis (Image Pro Plus, v.7, Media Cybernetics, USA) of

FESEM micrographs. Specimens were prepared for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) by cutting 3 mm diameter disks from the bulk of the as-sintered and annealed materials. Disks were mechanically ground down to about 20 μm thickness and then further ion beam thinned until perforations were observed by optical microscopy. Local phase analysis was performed using a FEI Tecnai F20 ST TEM, with an acceleration voltage of 200 kV. The TEM was equipped with an EDAX EDS X-ray spectrometer PV9761 with a super ultra-thin window.

Vickers microhardness (HV) was measured on polished surfaces, with a load of 9.81 N, using a Zwick 3212 tester (Ulm, Germany).

The 4-pt flexure strength (σ) was measured at room temperature (RT), in air at 1500°C and at 1800°C in Ar using the guidelines of the European standards for advanced ceramics ENV843-1:2006 and EN820-1:2002. Chamfered bars with dimensions 25.0 x 2.5 x 2.0 mm³ (length by width by thickness, respectively) were tested in four point bending at RT using a semi-articulated steel fixture (lower span 20 mm, upper span 10 mm) in a screw-driven load frame (Zwick-Roell mod. Z050, Germany), and a 1 mm/min cross-head speed. The tests in air at 1500°C were carried out using a screw-driven load frame (6025, Instron, Norwood, MA) equipped with a 4-pt fixture made of SiC. The tests at 1800°C in Argon were carried out using a custom-built apparatus consisting of a screw-driven instrumented load frame (33R4204, Instron, Norwood, MA), induction heated (SI-30KWLF, Superior Induction Technology, Pasadena, CA) graphite hot zone inside an environmental chamber using a fully articulated graphite fixture.[9] For flexure tests performed in a protective environment, the chamber was purged with argon for approximately 90 min prior to heating. Before applying the load during testing at elevated temperatures, a dwell of 12 min was set to allow specimens to reach thermal equilibrium. For each testing temperature, at least 3 bars were tested. The crosshead rate was 1 mm/min at room temperature and at 1500°C, but decreased to 0.5 mm/min at 1800°C.

3. Results

3.1 Microstructure

X-ray diffraction patterns of the hot pressed ceramic revealed that hexagonal HfB₂ was the main phase, red lines in Figure 1. In addition, new phases like WB, and possibly HfC, were also detected. These two phases are presumably reaction products resulting from surface oxide removal in the carbon-rich hot pressing chamber,[32] which could form by Reactions 1-3.

Figure 1: X-ray diffraction pattern of the as-sintered HfB₂-SiC-WC ceramic. The dotted lines evidence HfB₂ peak splitting at high angles.

Evidence of core-shell formation from HfB₂ peak splitting was difficult to detect and could be observed only at 2-theta angles above 110°. The experimental peak splitting (dotted lines in Figure 1) indicated that the shell phase had larger lattice parameters, which indicated a smaller unit cell. The lattice parameters of the W-containing HfB₂-based solid solution phase were $a = 3.1394 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 3.4714 \text{ \AA}$ compared to lattice parameters of $a = 3.1420 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 3.4760 \text{ \AA}$ for nominally pure HfB₂ (PDF # 38-1398). The amount of W dissolved in the HfB₂ cell was estimated to be between 2 and 4 at% based on Vegard's law [33] assuming lattice parameters of $a = 2.983 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 13.897 \text{ \AA}$ for nominally phase pure WB₂ (PDF # 43-1386).

Examples of the microstructure of the as-densified HfB₂-based ceramic are shown in Figure 2. The overall microstructure was free of processing flaws and had a homogeneous dispersion of secondary phases, Fig 2a. The newly formed WB phase exhibited brighter contrast and had irregularly shaped grains, whilst SiC grains appeared darker. The HfB₂ matrix was light gray with an average grain size of $1.1 \pm 0.4 \text{ \mu m}$ that appeared to be inhomogeneous. A closer view of the boride matrix, Fig 2b, revealed a shell with darker contrast around the core, which was the original HfB₂ particle. Formation of the shell was attributed to the formation of a W-containing solid solution, even though EDS analysis was not conclusive due to the low content of W dissolved in the HfB₂ and the similar energy of Hf and W M-line peaks. The W content was close to the EDS detection limit of around 2 at% [22] while the most intense M-lines for Hf and W were between 1.7 and 1.8 keV. Using channeling contrast, it was possible to identify line defects within the shell region in grains close to the Bragg condition, Figure 2c.[34] This feature was further confirmed by analysis

of fracture surfaces, where nanosized step-like fracture patterns were characteristic of the shell region, whereas flat, smooth transgranular fracture was typical of the core, Figure 2d&e. Occasionally, nano-sized bright precipitates were apparent on fracture surfaces of the shell, Figure 2e, suggesting refinement of the initial HfB_2 grain in this region. Notably, the WB phase, which contained about 4 at% of Hf, featured more pronounced step-like fracture features and bright inclusions, Figure 2f. As for the secondary phases, SiC maintained its sub-micron particle size, displayed a rounded shape, and tended to aggregate into 1-2 μm diameter clusters that were surrounded by a SiOC-based glass, Figure 2g. HfC grains had bright contrast as well and were found adjacent to WB, providing support for the occurrence of reactions (1-3).

Figure 2: SEM images of as-sintered HfB_2 ceramics showing a) the overall phases distribution, b) magnified view of the boride core-shell structure, c) line defects pointed by arrows, d)-e) the zig-zag fracture behavior of the shell and f) the WB phase, and g) the SiC particle clusters embedded in SiOC glassy phase. Below the EDS spectra recorded on HfB_2 , showing no appreciable chemical difference between core and shell, and on WB phase revealing possible Hf traces.

TEM analysis revealed that particles were trapped within boride grains. These particles were rounded and identified as HfO_2 , Figure 3a. The substructure of the boride grains, which resulted in

dislocation accumulation at the core/shell interface, was confirmed by Z contrast in Dark Field STEM mode, Figure 3b and Figure 4a. In this case, the L peak of tungsten at 7.36 keV was used for quantification. The compositional difference was further confirmed by an EDS profile across one grain or punctual, which revealed about 2-4 at% of W homogeneously dispersed in the shell, with a sharp shell/core boundary, and no detectable W in the grain core, Figure 3c&d and Figure 4b.

Figure 3: STEM images of the as-sintered HfB_2 ceramic showing a) trapped HfO_2 particles within a boride grain, b) Z-contrast dark field evidencing the boride substructure and c) & d) EDS profiles across one grain showing W enrichment in the shell.

Figure 4: STEM images of the as-sintered HfB_2 ceramic showing a) dislocation accumulation at the core/shell interface and b) corresponding EDS spectra in the two regions showing W enrichment in the shell.

After annealing, XRD patterns recorded at high 2-theta angles and shown in Figure 5 do not display the peak splitting, which is highlighted in the inset where patterns from as-sintered and annealed ceramics are compared. Based on this analysis, annealing appears to promote the decomposition of the (Hf,W)B₂ solid solution and return to a nominally pure HfB₂ phase.

Figure 5: X-ray diffraction pattern of the annealed HfB₂-SiC-WC ceramic. In the inset, the pattern of the as-sintered and annealed ceramics are overlapped evidencing different HfB₂ peak profiles.

The microstructure of the annealed HfB₂-SiC-WC ceramic is shown in Figure 6. The average boride grain size increased to $2.1 \pm 0.6 \mu\text{m}$ after annealing. Similarly, SiC particles coalesced to form platelets with flat edges that were about $2 \mu\text{m}$ across, whilst WB particles remained basically unchanged. Examination of the boride grains revealed that the size of the shells relative to the cores seemed to decrease, Figure 6b, and the amount of W in the shells also decreased, Figure 7a-c. The step-like features on the fracture surface that were only barely detected in the as-sintered ceramic were more pronounced in the annealed ceramic. The features on the fracture surface changed directions within the shell, possibly due to residual stress fields caused by the coarsening of the nano-sized bright inclusions. After annealing the bright inclusions were between 50 and 200 nm in diameter, had elongated shape, and were located between parallel facets within grains, Figure 6c&d. In addition, tiny holes could be found along fractured surfaces, presumably due to debonded nano-particles, Figure 6d, suggesting strong cohesion between the nano-particles and the

matrix. Based on Z-contrast and EDS, these particles appear to be W that has precipitated or coarsened inside the (Hf,W)B₂ shells during annealing.

Figure 6: a) SEM images of the annealed HfB₂ ceramic showing a) the overall phase distribution, b) magnified view of the boride core-shell structure with step-like ridges fracture surfaces in c)-d) shell, e) WB phase and f) SiC.

Figure 7: a)-b) STEM image of the annealed HfB_2 ceramic showing reduced shell extension with c) corresponding EDS spectra of core and shell and d) dislocation accumulation across one boride grain.

Crack arrest/initiation lines were identified across boride grains by a set of river patterns, which formed because of multiple cleavage steps produced when an extending crack passed through a grain boundary or when an arrested crack was re-initiated because crack propagation occurred in a slightly different orientation, Figure 6c,d. STEM analysis confirmed extended dislocation activity at the grain periphery, Figure 7d. Significant time and effort were devoted to the investigation of precipitates within the boride grains. Although the nano-inclusions were easily identified on fracture surfaces by SEM, they were difficult to observe by TEM due to similar contrast with the host grain, Figure 8. STEM evidenced that dislocations emanated from the particles and EDS confirmed W enrichment, Figure 8-9. Electron diffraction on one HfB_2 grain revealed the presence of additional spots corresponding to the inclusions, which could be indexed to metallic tungsten, Figure 9a-b. In a thick region of the TEM specimen, a grain boundary with step-like features that was decorated with W was observed, see the inset in Figure 8a. Polygonised dislocation walls were frequently encountered in the shell regions, Figure 8b.

Both WB and SiC displayed cleavage fracture with step-like ridges Figure 6e,f. Moreover, SiC platelets formed in the annealed ceramics. The platelets presumably resulted from merging of several rounded SiC particles in the as-sintered ceramics. The interfaces between HfB_2 grains, platelets, and the surrounding secondary phases appeared to be free of any grain boundary glassy phases, meaning that the grain

boundary phases were consumed during heat treatment, Figure 10. Finally, the SiC platelets exhibited cleavage across several planes, probably maintaining the orientation of the seed grains, Figure 6f.

Figure 8: a) STEM image of the annealed HfB₂ showing zig-zag fracture across grain boundary or the shell compared to straight fracture across the core, b)-c) evidence of nano-inclusions within the shell at dislocation sites.

Figure 9: STEM images of the annealed HfB_2 ceramic showing a) a grain overview with bright inclusions, b) diffraction patterns recorded on the grain far from the inclusions and on it, c) EDS profiles across the yellow path showing sudden W enrichment in correspondence of the inclusion and d) EDS spectrum on the inclusion.

Figure 10: a) HRTEM image and b) inverse Fourier-filtered image of the boxed area displaying clean grain boundaries at the triple junction between boride grains and SiC with the corresponding HfB_2 SAD pattern in c).

3.2 Mechanical properties

Hardness of the as-sintered ceramic was 21.9 ± 0.4 GPa, was higher than the value of 20.2 ± 0.2 GPa measured for the annealed ceramic. The decrease in hardness after annealing was attributed to the microstructural changes noted above, i.e. increase in grain size and precipitation of a metallic phase with lower hardness than the ceramic matrix.

Annealing resulted in a small decrease in the room-temperature strength, which was about 690 MPa in the as-sintered ceramic and around 570 MPa after annealing. In contrast, annealing improved the strength at elevated temperatures by about 300 MPa. Figure 11a shows the flexural strength as a function of the testing temperature. The strength of the as-sintered ceramic decreased to around 590 MPa at 1500°C in air and then to 320 MPa at 1800°C in an argon atmosphere, similar to the behavior exhibited by ZrB₂-ZrC-SiC ceramics.[31,35] In contrast, the flexural strength of the annealed ceramic was about 840 MPa at 1500°C in air and around 600 MPa at 1800°C in argon. The load-displacement curves for both materials were linear at 1500°C. However, the as-sintered ceramic displayed plasticity when tested at 1800°C as indicated by the decreasing slope in the load-displacement curve as extension increased, whereas the load-displacement curve for the annealed ceramic remained linear up to fracture, Figure 11b. Similarly, bars of the as-sintered ceramic were curved after testing at 1800°C, but annealed bars remained straight after testing at 1800°C.

The decrease in strength of both as-sintered and annealed ceramics as temperature increased from 1500°C to 1800°C may be related to simultaneous changes in the WB and W deformation mechanism, which has been shown to occur at about half of the melting temperature ($T_{\text{melt}} = 2740^\circ\text{C}$ for WB, so $0.6T_{\text{melt}}$ is 1644°C).[36,37]

For both ceramics, the microstructure of the fractured bars did not change when tested at 1800°C in argon. In contrast, testing in air at 1500°C resulted in formation of an oxidized scale that was around 20 μm thick. This layer was composed of HfO₂ with W metallic nano-inclusions and was topped by a thin silica glassy coating, analogous to what was observed in similar tests on ZrB₂-SiC-WC.[25]

The overall improved strength of the annealed ceramic was likely due, at least in part, to the reduction of residual glassy phase that surrounded the SiC particles, which reduced grain sliding and creep. Further beneficial effects of the annealed microstructure can be attributed to the evolution from the (Hf,W)B₂ shell to a nano-composite comprising HfB₂ with embedded W nano-inclusions as discussed below.

Figure 11:a) Flexural strength as a function of the testing temperature for HfB₂-based ceramics, and b) load-displacement curves for the two materials during test at 1800°C in argon showing different fracture behavior.

4. Discussion

4.1 Microstructure evolution: nano-composite development

Annealing ceramics can relieve residual stresses, homogenize/coarsen microstructures, or induce crystallization of amorphous phases. In the present study, annealing at 2100°C was performed with the aim of inducing microstructural changes both in the boride matrix and SiC particles. Regarding SiC, the evolution from sub-micron rounded particles to elongated platelets was expected based on observations in other studies.[38–40] In addition, annealing further reduced residual glassy phases around SiC particles, which was detrimental to the high temperature strength of the as-sintered ceramics, Figure 2g&6f. Annealing successfully altered the SiC morphology and improved elevated temperature mechanical behavior, as demonstrated by SEM analysis, and increased elevated temperature strength.

The boride matrix was also affected by annealing. The mean grain size increased, but the prolonged dwell at 2100°C also continued phenomena that had presumably started during densification. In this case, the grain shells showed traces of grain refinement on the fracture surface and tiny bright segregations in the as-sintered specimens, Figure 8a, indicating that the W content in the shell may have been near the saturation limit at the sintering temperature of 1930°C. Relevant studies confirm the low solubility of W in either HfB₂ or ZrB₂, which further decreases from a maximum at the eutectic temperatures above 2200°C to nearly zero below ~1400°C.[22,41–45] In the Zr-W-B system, a maximum solubility of 13 at% at the eutectic temperature of 2230°C was estimated,[41] whilst a much lower solubility of 3 at% of W in ZrB₂ was reported at 2100°C with excess W segregating at the grain boundaries.[44] In the Hf-W-B system, the maximum solid solubility of W in HfB₂ at the eutectic temperature of ~2309°C corresponds to a (Hf_{0.77}W_{0.23})B₂ composition, where W amount is analogously reduced as temperature decreases.[46] Moreover, the solubility of W in the boride lattice is further decreased with presence of carbon.[45] In the carbon-rich environment in the hot press used for densification, we found maximum dissolved W contents between 2 and 6 at%, in agreement with equilibria phases studies.

The subsequent heat treatment at 2100°C promoted decomposition of the initial (Hf,W)B₂ solid solution to a new more energetically favorable W-depleted (Hf,W)B₂ solid solution and metallic tungsten nanoparticles precipitated uniformly as shown by the inset in Figure 6d and sketched in Figure 12. Annealing undoubtedly emphasized the refined structure of the shell that had started during densification, and enabled continued development of the nano-composite.

Previous studies have shown that core-shell structures develop in boride ceramics due to solid state diffusion during densification at high temperature.[20,24] At the densification temperature of 1930°C used in the present study, grain boundary diffusion is the predominant sintering mechanism and W solubility is relatively low. The W does not diffuse into the cores, which are remnants of the original HfB₂ particles, because lattice diffusion is not active below about 2100°C.[47] During cooling, the thermal expansion coefficient mismatch between the core and shell leads to dislocation pile-up at the interface, Figure 4a,

whilst W exceeding the solubility limit within HfB_2 lattice precipitates and promotes twinning in the shells, Figure 2e. At the annealing temperature of 2100°C , W solubility is higher so local W concentrations can increase. During cooling from the annealing high temperature, W solubility is again exceeded locally in the shells due to the decrease in W solubility with temperature. Nucleation and coarsening of inclusions are facilitated in the shells due to the presence of the defects (i.e., dislocation pile-ups and twins). In the final microstructure, the W particles constitute flaws within the boride matrix and trigger preferential fracture along twin planes. This is consistent by the zig-zag fracture observed in the shell region, which is subjected to a different stress state as compared to the core where the fracture is transgranular, Figure 8a. The same mechanism is expected for the other solid solution present in the system, $(\text{W,Hf})\text{B}$, which exhibits the same fracture type, Figure 6a. This configuration could be beneficial for elevated temperature fracture, since crack-tip deflection occurs near surface instabilities caused by dopant atoms or phase segregation [48]. An analogous transition from a mixed inter/transgranular fracture mode in a monolithic ceramic to pure transgranular mode with zig-zag features was observed for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}$ nano-composites when nanoinclusions were located within the matrix, which was attributed to a grain boundary strengthening.[49]

The surface area/volume ratio is several orders of magnitudes higher for nanoscale grains than for microscale grains. This implies, as a first consequence, that the properties of ceramic composites containing nanoscale inclusions tend to be influenced by the properties of the inclusions and/or inclusion-grain interfaces.[2] The micro-nano-composite configuration is particularly suited for improving the mechanical performance at elevated temperatures, since W is ductile and has much higher toughness than the ceramic, particularly above 400°C , and is thus able to absorb significant fracture energy.[50]

Figure 12: Sketch of the nano-composite evolution within the shell from the as-sintered to the annealed state.

4.2 Fracture behavior: shell strengthening

The Griffith equation indicates that the strength of brittle materials can be increased by increasing fracture toughness, K_{Ic} , decreasing the flaw size, a , or both. When other, larger defects are eliminated, the critical flaw size is typically the grain size. In the present case, the overall boride grains coarsened during annealing from about $1.1 \mu\text{m}$ in the as-sintered ceramics to about $2.1 \mu\text{m}$ after annealing, which should decrease

strength. However, if the inner sub-structure of each grain is considered, the characteristic size within the shell structure reduced by about one order of magnitude, Figure 8b, which should increase strength. In parallel, toughness may also increase based on the analogous toughening effect of the dispersed SiC nanoparticles which has been described for matrices of Al_2O_3 , S_3N_4 or Y_2O_3 with micron sized grains.[51–54] In particular, surface roughening and crack shielding are probable based on the microstructures observed in the present study. In the present case, cracks propagated straight across the grain cores and then changed direction upon entering shells or crossing grain boundaries, Figure 2d,6d,8a. As a result, the fractured surface of the boride grains is similar to that of typical soda-lime-silica glasses sketched in Figure 13a,[55] where the mirror region corresponds to the HfB_2 core, which is bounded by a narrow band of rougher mist that transitions into an even rougher hackle region with large, aligned facets and nano-inclusions that comprise the nano-composite. Changes in roughness moving from one region to the other are associated with changes in crack energy.[55] In the core, under constant loading, fracture is unstable and excess energy is available to drive the crack, so that the crack accelerates rapidly. When the crack encounters the nanocomposite shell, it may slow, or even stop briefly, before following the twin sub-structure, which results in mist and hackle formation. Fractography is consistent with cracks crossing grains in discontinuous steps, which suggests that the fracture toughness tends to increase locally in the shell regions, Figure 8a. In such a situation, the applied stress has to increase to move the crack front.

We speculate that two factors may contribute to a local strength increase in the shell regions at elevated temperatures. First, nanoscale crack deflection at twin boundaries dissipates energy to sites of lower stress concentration [56] creating a wavy crack path that enlarges the area of the crack surface and increases the toughness by absorbing more energy during fracture, Figure 13b. The degree of toughening caused by formation of a wavy fracture surface has been estimated for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}$ nanocomposites with toughness increasing steeply for particle volume fractions (V_f) below 10% and then decreasing for higher particle contents due to the formation of direct cracks.[54] The barrier effect induced by twist misorientations at grain boundaries has also been noted in dedicated studies, where the steps for the crossing of a twist grain boundary by a cleavage crack are clearly indicated.[57,58] In the present case, W inclusions weaken the atomic planes and promote cleavage cracking. In addition, the WB leads to a very tortuous fracture surface and may also contribute to toughening.

Figure 13: a) Sketch of the arrangement of the fracture surface across one boride grain suggesting different fracture speed across core and shell, b) SEM fracture surface pointing to nanoscale deflection across the shell and WB and c) possible pull-out and bridging mechanisms of W nano-inclusions between HfB_2 facets within the shell.

Second, nanosized metallic W inclusions increase toughness due to their ductility. The toughness of W increases as temperature increases, from $5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\sqrt{\text{m}}$ at room temperature to values as high as $80 \text{ MPa}\cdot\sqrt{\text{m}}$ at elevated temperatures.[50] Metallic nano-inclusions could shield the crack tip and bridge the crack, Figure 13c. Toughening effects were found to be maximized in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}$ nano-composites for $V_f = 8.5 \text{ vol}\%$. When V_f was higher or lower, the clinching effects decreased because the crack surface became relatively flat [54]. The amount of W dispersed in our boride shell is estimated to be around 10 vol% based on image analysis. Elongated W particles were observed on fracture surfaces, so crack bowing and crack deflection are here proposed as the toughening mechanisms when metallic W nano-inclusions are embedded in a HfB_2 ceramic matrix.

Hence, we believe that the observation of smooth grain cores and ragged shells with W particles on the fracture surface indicates that “stick-slip” crack propagation occurred, which increased the applied stress needed for crack growth across shells at elevated temperatures.[59,60]

Strengthening approaches are always of great interest for brittle ceramics. Likewise, increased fracture toughness can considerably reduce the number of components wasted due to failure during production and increase reliability during service. In this work, we have identified mechanisms that improve the strength, and possibly the fracture toughness, of bulk ceramics up to 1800°C as summarized in Table I. This table highlights the improved performance of the annealed ceramic that developed the nano-composite structure over those of the as-sintered one.

Table I: List of possible strengthening mechanisms active in the HfB₂-SiC-WC materials.

Mechanism	Behavior	Sintered	Annealed
Grain boundaries (gb) and grain size	small grain-sized materials have a large number of gb and various grain orientations. Dislocations (<i>d</i>) must change direction, deviating from their unimpeded paths. The slip systems, the planes and directions dictating <i>d</i> motion, vary from grain to grain, and <i>d</i> motion is deflected complicating the crack path (Hall-Petch law)	yes	yes
Clean grain junctions	a glassy phase at grain boundaries may lead to creep under applied stress at high temperature and compromise the strength	Glassy pockets	yes
Solution strengthening	W atoms act as obstacles to <i>d</i> glide, which is pinned and <i>d</i> must climb them to continue motion in other planes	yes	W amount too low
Precipitation hardening	precipitates rejected from supersaturated solid solutions act as obstacles to <i>d</i> motion. Stress must increase to push the <i>d</i> through it making the material harder and stronger	very small	yes
Twinning	Twin boundaries are coherent and nano-sized internal boundaries enable strengthening while preserving ductility	very thin twins	yes
Grain pullout	Strong grains form bridges across cracks before failing and thus inhibiting brittle rupture of the material	yes (WB)	yes (SiC, WB, W)
Particle bridging	Ductile particles bridge cracks and suppress crack growth; at the same time ductile particles plastically deform absorbing additional fracture energy	very small	yes
Ductile deformation	W is ductile and tough at elevated temperature and absorbs energy during crack propagation	no	yes

5. Conclusions

This work demonstrated that annealing increased the mechanical strength of HfB₂-SiC-WC ceramics at elevated temperatures by promoting the development of nanocomposite structures. The annealed ceramic had a strength of more than 840 MPa at 1500°C and above 600 MPa at 1800°C, which were both about 300 MPa higher than the as-sintered ceramic tested at the same temperatures.

The microstructure of the as-sintered material was characterized by a core-shell structure with shells composed of a (Hf,W)B₂ solid solution and grain cores of pure HfB₂. The shells exhibited nano-texturing owing to the precipitation of W nanoparticles. Agglomerates of SiC and WB grains were observed in the as-sintered ceramic. Upon annealing, SiC coalesced to form platelets and residual glassy pockets around SiC particles crystallized leaving mostly clean grain boundaries. The (Hf,W)B₂ solid solution decomposed into HfB₂ with homogeneously dispersed W nano-inclusions.

Thermal annealing has been demonstrated to be a simple and convenient method for improving the elevated temperature mechanical properties of boride-based ceramics. Annealing led to reduction of glassy pockets surrounding SiC particles and promoted merging of SiC particle clusters into single platelets, which contributed to toughening by grain pull-out. In addition, annealing enabled development of a nanocomposite structure in the shell regions with homogeneously distributed nano-sized metallic W inclusions embedded in HfB₂, which locally strengthened the ceramic by increasing energy absorption during crack propagation through crack deflection and deformation of ductile nano-inclusions.

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Data availability

The raw and processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time due to legal or ethical reasons.

Conflict of Interest

The authors certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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